

تصویر کی شرعی حیثیت

Picture in the light of Shariah

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Abstract

This article examines the concept of imagery and the role of pictures within the framework of Islamic teachings. It explores historical, theological, and cultural perspectives regarding the creation and use of images in Islam. By analyzing primary texts, including the Qur'an and Hadith, along with interpretations from classical and contemporary scholars, the article addresses critical questions about the permissibility of pictures in various contexts such as art, education, and personal use. The discussion highlights the diverse opinions within Islamic jurisprudence, considering factors like intent, purpose, and the nature of depicted subjects. Additionally, it reflects on the influence of modern technology and digital media on traditional views of imagery. Ultimately, this article aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the role of pictures in Islam, fostering thoughtful dialogue on their significance in contemporary society.

Keywords: : Imagery, Islam, Pictures, Qur'an, Hadith, Islamic Jurisprudence, Cultural Perspectives, Digital Media, Permissibility.

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